

APPENDIX A – INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Investigating the Online Recruitment and Selection Journey of Novice Software Engineers: Anti-patterns and Recommendations

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1. About the Study:

The aim of this research is to identify a set of antipatterns and recommended practices suggested by recruiters for entry-level professionals in the online recruitment and selection process for positions in the field of Software Engineering.

2. Who Can Participate?

Professionals from technology-based companies engaged in online recruitment and selection activities for software engineers for over one year, whether in roles such as recruiters, managers, or tech leads.

3. What Will Be Requested?

Upon your consent to participate in the research, a questionnaire will commence, requesting responses to questions about personal and professional/academic information.

4. Your Rights and Responsibilities as a Participant:

Participation in this research poses no risks to you. Your involvement is entirely voluntary.

- You have the right to refuse to participate.
- You can stop at any time, even after granting permission.
- You are not required to provide a reason for discontinuing your participation, and it will have no consequences.
- If you start but terminate your participation before completing the survey, all your data will be discarded for analysis.
- You have the right to know the general results of the research, which will be disseminated through the project that will be carried out.

The information obtained will be stored electronically by the researchers, and only the research team will have access to this data. The data will be electronically stored in a database on the researchers' computers, processed ANONYMOUSLY, assigning a personal code that does not allow participant identification.

We guarantee that the treatment of your data will be as careful as during the initial collection. The study results will be used solely for scientific purposes, conference presentations, and the creation of scientific publications.

5. Compensation:

You will not receive any compensation for participating in this study, even in the case of adverse events.

6. Risks:

The only risk associated with participating in this study is a small degree of emotional involvement when answering questions. In this case, you may stop responding and resume when you deem appropriate or definitively stop participating.

If you have questions or comments about the research, please email us at our correspondence addresses. If, during the study, you have any comments or concerns about the conduct of the research or questions about your rights when participating in the study, you may contact one of the evaluators.

We appreciate your participation in this research in advance.

Do you authorize and agree to all the points presented in the consent form?

Yes, I fully agree with the presented terms.